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Teaching Listening Comprehension in English Lessons and the Typology of Exercises for Developing This Type of Speech Activity

Abstract: The article examines the concept of listening comprehension, its relationship with other types of speech activity, types and stages of listening, and provides sample exercises for developing and improving this skill.

Key words: Listening comprehension, speech activity, English language, listening exercise.

In recent years, teaching communication in a foreign language, particularly English, has become a top priority. In the modern world, English is considered not just a foreign language but also an international one, mastery of which is essential for obtaining a quality education, securing a high-paying job, and communicating effectively on a global scale. Proficiency in English encompasses all aspects of language skills: speaking, reading, listening, and writing. The development and improvement of these skills occur in a complex, interconnected manner.

Recently, the greatest attention has been given to teaching listening comprehension, as true language proficiency implies the ability to freely understand English speech by ear. The mastery of spoken language begins with listening. By perceiving information aurally, learners master the sound aspects of the language, including its intonation patterns. Proficiency in this type of speech activity helps individuals hear and understand speakers, extract necessary information, respond to interlocutors' speech, and convey required information, which in turn constitutes speaking. The acquisition of any language, especially one's native tongue, starts with listening: we hear sounds and words, perceiving any stream of information aurally, and only then do we learn to reproduce speech (speaking), followed by learning reading and writing skills. Thus, listening is a crucial and primary link in the language learning process. Listening serves as both the goal and the means of language instruction¹⁸.

¹⁸ Соловова Е. Н. Методика обучения иностранным языкам: Базовый курс лекций: Пособие для студентов пед. вузов и учителей. — М.: Просвещение, 2003. — 124 стр.

Every lesson includes this kind of speaking exercise, in which the teacher speaks and the pupils respond. Speaking skills can also be developed by listening to audio recordings; writing a letter, essay, presentation, etc., can help develop writing skills; dictation or presentation also requires listening; in these situations, listening is a tool for teaching speech activities, and listening perception is a secondary factor. J.L. Vitin refers to this as an audition for learning. Teaching the speaker to comprehend the language by ear is the aim of listening training. According to J.L. Vitin, "communicative listening." In this case, we already need to consider the approaches and strategies required for a certain kind of speech activity¹⁹.

The most important component of teaching listening is motivation. The requirement for auditory perception must exist in the listener. It's crucial to pick an audio text that will appeal to kids' interests, age-related traits, and youth issues while still being engaging and educational (for instance, a text about a certain nation). There are many other ways to listen these days, such as podcasts, audiobooks, movies, English-language music, radio broadcasts, and television channels. It is advised that the audio content be connected to the unit being studied in class. This will cut down on the amount of time required figuring out previously taught vocabulary within the context of the discussion subject and prevent the logical flow of information from being disrupted.

The student's degree of preparation and the sounding text's loudness must be taken into account while choosing a text for listening. It is the teacher's responsibility to help students perceive the text and to rule out any potential grammatical, lexical, or phonetic issues before they ever hear it. They are differentiated based on the task:

- Listening with full understanding of the text;
- Listening with understanding of the main content;
- Auditing with selective extraction of information.

The possibility of giving the student a printed copy of the text after they finish the assignments is not excluded when they are listening with a complete comprehension of the text ("detailed listening") (listening for detailed information) in order to help them identify words they may have missed or unclear phrases, as well as to practice self-control. When listening to a poetry or music, this is applicable. A great deal of memory and focus are required for detailed listening. It is sufficient to deliver the text twice while listening with comprehension of the primary material

¹⁹ Vitin J. L. *Modern Methods of Teaching and Studying Foreign Languages*. - Saint Petersburg: KARO, 1997. P-108.

(skim listening). You can pause briefly after the logically finished paragraph if the text is substantial enough for a second hearing.

The ability to distinguish and retain the primary information while disregarding the secondary and superfluous information is developed when listening for partial understanding, where one hearing is sufficient. There are three phases of listening training:

- Before listening;
- While listening;
- After listening.

The first stage involves a teacher-student dialogue. The first task is to prepare and tune it into listening. It is possible to present visual supports where the title of the text is present; unfamiliar or complex, in the teacher's opinion, vocabulary; as well as an illustration (possibly a photo or picture) that is related to the text. Let us consider a specific example of a lesson with first-year language students in a higher education institution. Within the framework of studying the topic "There is no place like home," students are offered to listen to a country-language audio recording called "Life without a ray of sun." The text tells the story of a small underground city in Australia, Kuber Pedi, known as the capital of the opals.

The tasks in the pre-text stage can be as follows:

- What do you think this text will be about? (subject to title);
- What unusual places for living do you know?;
- Look at the picture and tell where the flat is located and how it looks like? (pictures from the internet can be used as visual aids).

Grammar and selected vocabulary are unavoidably emphasized. Type of assignment:

1. Make up your own sentences with new words. You may set up the work so that others can focus, learn new terms, and improve their listening skills by having the first person read in English while the second person translates the lines into Russian. This will allow others to listen intently to the examples of their peers.

The purpose of the exercises at this stage is to prepare students for listening, introduce them to the topic, motivate them to work, and remove any lexical or grammatical difficulties if they exist. In the next, textual stage, students listen to the text; try to understand the main content, the theme of the text, the main facts. Before listening, you can give tasks like:

- Listen to the text and tell what sort of text it is (for example a description, an opinion article, a narrative).

- Listen to the text and think of your own heading.

- Guess what...?. If the text is not of a country study nature, but describes some situation or incident from the life of the narrator, then you can pause during the listening and ask the students to predict, to guess how and what the narration will end.

The post-text stage offers unlimited opportunities for checking the understanding of the listened material, as well as for parallel improvement of skills in other types of speech activity. The tasks in the post-text stage can be as follows:

1. Fill in the gaps.
2. Are the sentences true or false? If the sentence is false, correct it.
3. Put the sentences in chronological order.
4. Choose the correct answer.
5. Match two halves of the sentence.
6. Make a plan of the text.
7. Make up your own questions based on the text.
8. Do you remember what these numbers mean?

These assignments simultaneously improve writing and reading skills. Another group of post-text exercises is aimed at improving speaking skills. These include exercises such as:

1. Answer the questions.
2. Choose the best summary.
3. Discuss with your partner.
4. Choose the proverb (think of a proverb) according to the text.
5. Do you agree or disagree with the narrator?
6. Whom do you agree with? Give your own arguments. Such an

assignment is suitable if the audio recording represents the expression of the opinions of several people on a certain problem.

The number of exercises will depend on the level of training, activity and interest of the students, as well as the number of hours spent in the lesson. Therefore, learning to listen is a fairly interesting, rich, educational and cognitive process, if the student is properly motivated. Mastering this skill ensures the success of communication, which lies in the ability to speak English and understand English speech. In addition to its main goal, listening develops memory, thinking, imagination, and perception, that is, it contributes to the comprehensive development of the individual.

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